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The National Museum of Geology in Ampandrianomby: An Educational Device for the Earth Sciences in Madagascar

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Abstract

The National Museum of Geology in Ampandrianomby (MNG) is a flagship institution for the Earth Sciences in Madagascar. Its heritage value rests on a collection of around 27,000 geological specimens, bearing witness to a remarkable mineral and fossil diversity. Yet this potential remains underused by secondary education, where museum visits are often occasional and have little bearing on the curricula, even though they could play a decisive role in the transmission of scientific knowledge. This qualitative research, rooted in Information and Communication Sciences draws on five complementary theoretical frameworks —Palo Alto, Goffman, Hymes, Mucchielli, and Chevallard— in order to analyze museum mediation as practiced at the MNG and its effects on high-school students' appropriation of geological concepts. Findings show the pedagogical value of certain interactional moments with students, while highlighting persistent tensions between the museum's heritage mission and the implicit constraints of the school context. These constraints tend to restrict learners' sensory engagement and create discontinuities in the process of knowledge transmission. To address these obstacles and promote sustainable appropriation of the museum by school audiences, the study proposes an innovative operational device: the “geo-didactic mediation spiral.” This model aims to increase the scientific capital of Malagasy students by integrating museum resources more closely into educational practices.

Keywords

museum mediation, geology, didactic transposition, educational communication

Setting the scene: Ampandrianomby's geology museum and its audiences

Although Law no. 2006-030 officially recognizes museums in Madagascar as major actors in civic education and non-formal education, their integration into the formal education system remains limited. Founded in 1923 by Henri Bésairie and Alfred Lacroix, the National Museum of Geology in Ampandrianomby (MNG) illustrates this situation well: despite a remarkable collection of roughly 27,000 geological pieces, links with schools are episodic and rely mainly on individual initiatives rather than on institutional and sustainable collaboration. The primary objective of this research is to assess how museum mediation at the MNG affects high-school students' acquisition of geological knowledge. Our guiding question is: can the museum—an environment of objects, narratives, and actions—become a genuine extension of the Life and Earth Sciences (SVT) course rather than a pedagogical interlude? More precisely, under what

conditions does a visit to the MNG promote the acquisition, mobilization, and reuse of geological concepts at the high-school level? This question arises in a concrete context: many institutions lack material samples to illustrate mineralogy. School outings therefore meet the need to embody knowledge, but they expose themselves to another difficulty — the alignment between heritage and educational frameworks. On the one hand, guides carry the mission of enhancing the collections and the nation's geological wealth; on the other, the teacher aims for specific curricular goals (for example, distinguishing mineral from ore), expects tangible evidence, and seeks mediations that can be reused in class. Students' experience thus oscillates between heritage admiration and educational focus, at the risk of fragmented attention and incomplete learning. To grasp this complexity, the article is anchored in the Sciences of Information and Communication and mobilizes five complementary theoretical frameworks —not simply juxtaposed but used successively to illuminate the mechanisms of mediation: the transactional model from the Palo Alto school (feedback loops that densify exchange), Goffman's interactionism (coordination of frames of experience and roles), Hymes's socio-pragmatic perspective (weight of implicit norms and linguistic keys), Mucchielli's teleological approach (trade-offs between scientific, heritage, and institutional goals), and Chevallard's didactic transposition (continuity among scholarly knowledge, taught knowledge, and exhibited knowledge). Together, these models provide a framework that connects the moment of interaction, the social organization of the visit, the tacit rules governing it, its purposes, and the necessary articulation with the SVT curriculum. Empirically, the study is based on a triangulated qualitative framework: semi-structured interviews with museum actors and one grade-10 class; participant observation of guided visits; and documentary analysis of labels and internal materials. This approach identifies, as closely as possible to the field, what works—those interactional 'clicks' where a high school student's question reconfigures the guide's presentation —and what hinders appropriation—anti-tactile norms, lack of audiovisual support, dispersed aims, and breaks in didactic transposition. We then propose an operational model—the geo-didactic mediation spiral—which articulates four recurrent movements: object (secure touching and choice of robust samples), narrative (situated and bilingual contextualization), manipulation (guided workshops that turn observation into investigation), and question (co-construction through dialogue and a culture of feedback). Our underlying hypothesis is that, if assumed and tooled, this orchestration can transform a one-off visit into a sustainable and reusable learning experience in class. The contribution of the article is twofold. Analytically, it shows that difficulties often attributed to a 'lack of resources' in fact reflect issues of framing, norms, and didactic alignment—dimensions the five models help unpack. Operationally, it provides a device testable in situ—the spiral—together with simple indicators to evaluate effects (pre/post, delayed recall, interaction metrics along the route), in the spirit of explicit, curriculum-linked museum mediation. The remainder of the article clarifies the theoretical foundations mobilized, describes the methodological and ethical protocol, presents empirical results, develops each phase of the spiral, and then offers a discussion with the literature. Before concluding on the limitations, research perspectives, and concrete recommendations for the MNG.

Complementary Conceptual Frameworks for Understanding Museum Mediation

The analysis draws on five complementary theoretical frameworks conceived as an

architecture of complementarity to examine, from interrelated perspectives, the museum's communication and educational practices. Taken together, they cover the entire communication process from the micro-dynamics of interaction to overall pedagogical coherence. This combination is not merely decorative: it becomes operational in the geo-didactic mediation spiral proposed below, where objects, narratives, gestures, and questions are orchestrated according to these five perspectives.

1) Transactional model (Palo Alto): interaction as a driver of appropriation—The Palo Alto school reminds us that 'one cannot not communicate': postures, silences, glances, micro-gestures—everything informs the other and requires adjustment ¹. Communication is conceived as a circular and co-constructed process; where the sender and receiver continuously adjust their behaviors via feedback. In the museum context, this perspective helps explain how, during a guided tour, a student's question, a mediator's gesture, or a moment's hesitation in front of a display case can immediately redirect the exchange—either opening space for exploration or constraining it. The heuristic value of the model lies in its ability to capture the immediacy of these interactional regulations (analog/digital, verbal/non-verbal), which are decisive for audience engagement.

2) Goffman's interactionism: articulating experiential frames and roles—The visit unfolds at the intersection of distinct frameworks ²: the heritage framework (celebrating a heritage, telling a national story) and the academic framework (mastering life sciences concepts, meeting curricular expectations). By focusing on these interpretive frameworks, roles, and the staging of the situation (frontstage/backstage), Goffman situates the exchanges in their institutional and historical environment: educational context (academic expectations, implicit assessments) versus heritage context (preservation, sanctification of objects). "Situations are framed: roles and expectations guide interpretation." — ². Goffman's theory then calls for alignment work beforehand—a short guide-teacher briefing—and framework reminders during the visit ("for our purpose today, let us remember..."). This grid sheds light on the role shifts—teacher, guide, student—that sometimes generate friction (for example, when the guide prioritizes the heritage narrative while the teacher seeks curricular explanation), and shows how these shifts reconfigure the "framework" of the activity. Making frameworks explicit upstream (brief guide-teacher briefing) and during the visit helps align expectations.

3) Dell Hymes's socio-pragmatic model: norms, languages, and "keys" to the situation — Through the ethnography of communication (SPEAKING), Hymes introduces the cultural and normative dimension of exchanges. The Setting (exhibition room), the Key (serious or playful tone), the Norms (expected behaviors in a museum context), and the Genre (visit, workshop, lecture) guide the interpretation of messages and the degree of permitted sensorimotor engagement. As he said: "SPEAKING 'keys' shape reception and participation." — ³. This approach highlights the effect of implicit norms (whispering, not touching, moving slowly) on reception and, consequently, on the quality of knowledge acquisition.

4) Alex Mucchielli's teleological perspective—Mediation unfolds within an ecology of purposes ⁴: scientific (accuracy, rigor), heritage (promotion, pride), institutional (image, attendance), pedagogical (learning), logistical (time, flow, materials)—which can converge or conflict. Making these goals explicit, as well as the material (visit time, staffing, accessibility of facilities) and organizational (coordination with institutions,

school calendar) constraints, contributes to the clarity of the museum's discourse and the alignment of actions (choice of objects, sequencing, media). A clear statement of goals serves as a compass to arbitrate between sometimes competing demands. In this spiral, Mucchielli justifies the sobriety of objectives, the limited selection of manipulable samples, and the economy of gestures that make the visit operationally viable.

5) Yves Chevallard's didactic transposition: alignment as a requirement— The didactic heart of the enterprise lies in the continuity between scholarly knowledge, taught knowledge, and exhibited knowledge ⁵. This framework is therefore essential for analyzing the continuity of knowledge from scholarly knowledge (academic geology) to taught knowledge (SVT curriculum) and exhibited knowledge (labels, devices, museum narratives). It allows us to identify where and how potential breaks occur (hasty simplifications, unstable metaphors, dissociation between curriculum and exhibition content) that weaken the effectiveness of teaching.

As with museum devices, for example: Labels should be designed as links in the transposition chain. If it is too elliptical, it does not lend itself well to academic reuse; if it is too technical, it disrupts understanding. Chevallard leads us to design didactic devices (double entry notion/context, minimal lexicon, pivotal question) and tasks that link the gesture to the notion (observe → compare → name → classify). Mobilized at this level, the didactic transposition establishes the feasibility of the spiral: Object (perceptual anchoring) → Story (contextualization) → Manipulation (procedure) → Question (conceptualization), each step contributing to reversibility in the classroom. The challenge is to maintain a sufficiently homogeneous chain of transposition so that the visit experience reinforces, and does not short-circuit, school learning.

Articulation: From Micro to Curriculum, a Visit Engineering

Taken together, these frameworks form a visit design engineering. The articulation of these five models offers a coherent overall view: from the micro level (interactional adjustments: Palo Alto equips the micro-adjustments that bring the exchange to life) to the meso level (frameworks, roles, norms: Goffman stabilizes expectations by clarifying the framework; Hymes opens access through the deliberate management of norms and codes) and to the macro level (purposes, didactic continuity: Mucchielli disciplines the purposes to avoid dispersion; Chevallard ensures curricular alignment). This articulation supports our spiral modeling and guides the methodology: we observe the interactions (Palo Alto), document the framings and roles (Goffman), identify the norms/languages and their explanation (Hymes), identify trade-offs among purposes (Mucchielli) and audit the didactic quality of the supports (Chevallard) which led to formalizing the geo-didactic mediation spiral, an operational framework grounded in a solid theoretical base, designed to guide the design, evaluation and continuous improvement of mediations at the National Museum of Geology. In short, these five frameworks, far from neutralizing each other, respond to each other. They make visible what often goes unseen—the invisible rules of the situation, the choices that orient speech, the chains that carry one from an object to a concept — and provide concrete levers for turning a one-off visit into a sustainable learning experience.

An In-Depth Qualitative Analysis

Research design and fieldwork

The study is based on an in-depth qualitative approach, designed to capture as closely as possible the real dynamics of mediation at the National Museum of Geology in Ampandrianomby (MNG), Antananarivo. The design relies on a triangulation that combines semi-structured interviews, participant observation of guided tours, and documentary analysis of exhibition support and internal documents. This choice aims less at statistical representativeness than at descriptive depth and the intelligibility of processes, in line with the orientation of Information and Communication Sciences.

Participants and corpus

The sample includes nineteen semi-structured interviews: the head of department at the MNG, a Life and Earth Sciences (SVT) teacher, and fifteen students in Seconde (10th grade) from a public high school in the capital. The students, aged 15 to 20, were interviewed individually immediately after the visit to elicit situated impressions and minimize retrospective reconstruction. The teacher—who had scheduled the outing within the “Mineralogy” chapter—was interviewed about preparation, curricular expectations, and how the visit would be used in class. Discussions with the guides and the head of department addressed the organization of group visits, prevailing rules (touching, photography), available resources, and mediation trade-offs.

These interviews, supplemented by two participant observation sessions, totaling approximately six hours, were conducted during regular guided tours.. They provided an opportunity to observe the conduct of the mediation, the flow of visitors, moments of attention or disengagement, and interactions among guides, students, and the teacher. Finally, a documentary analysis was carried out on object labels and the internal documents provided, in order to assess the structure and informational density of the materials on display.

Analysis strategy: aligning frameworks with protocol

The empirical materials were processed in three stages. First, inductive coding surfaced a set of recurrent themes (including: lack of samples at school, the visit’s school function, tension between heritage and school frames, norms and languages, interactional “clicks,” audiovisual expectations, organizational constraints). Second, these themes were re-read deductively in light of the five models mobilized, to establish solid correspondences between empirical data and conceptual frameworks. The choice of instruments was based on the frameworks. The semi-structured interviews, in the transactional spirit of Palo Alto, aimed to document the feedback loops that shift a lecture into an interaction (spontaneous questions, reformulations, reprises). The observation grid, inspired by Goffman, records declared framings and markers of frame and role shifts; Hymes’s socio-pragmatic register codes explicit norms, their managed suspension, paralinguistic clues, and linguistic alternation; Mucchielli provided the grid of purposes and constraints structuring mediation choices; and Chevallard finally served as a compass for assessing alignment between scholarly knowledge, taught knowledge, and displayed knowledge. This transposition audit, drawing on Chevallard, examines the presence of an explicit curricular notion, a minimal lexicon, instructions, and a bridge back to the classroom. This combined inductive/deductive entry ensured traceability of interpretations: each inference corresponds to an empirical anchor in the interviews, observation, or materials. Finally, a targeted content analysis compared the official SVT curriculum’s

“Mineralogy” chapter with the museum’s resources (labels, guided tours) to verify alignment between curricular objectives and the information actually presented.

Curricular anchoring and Materials Audit

“An exhibition is a communication device organizing objects, signs, and pathways.” — 6. Given the explicit positioning of the outing within the SVT “Mineralogy” chapter, a curricular alignment check was conducted. It compared the unit’s key notions (e.g., the distinction between mineral and ore, rock families, formation processes) with the contents actually mobilized along the route and with the wording of the labels. The aim was not to assess the patrimonial value of the pieces, but to identify breakdowns in didactic transposition likely to hinder classroom reuse: overly elliptical headings, lack of procedural guidance (how to observe, compare, classify), lack of explicit links to academic terminology. This audit informed the modeling developed later—the spiral of geo-didactic mediation— by specifying the minimum didactic requirements for each phase (object, narrative, manipulation, question).

Data collection procedures

The interviews were conducted in French, with occasional alternations in Malagasy when this facilitated the participants' expression. The audio recordings, supplemented by field notes, provided the basis for faithful transcripts, lightly smoothed for readability without altering meaning. The verbatim transcripts reproduced in the manuscript have been pseudonymized for the students (assumed first names) and functionally designated for the museum staff (Guide #1, Guide #2, Head of Department).

Participant observation followed a low-profile protocol: the researcher integrated himself into the group, limiting interventions to moments of explicitly solicited exchange. Field notes recorded the outline of the visit, the content of guides’ prompts and reformulations, students’ audiovisual expectations, and the tangible effects of rules on engagement (notably the tactile frustration associated with “do not touch”).

Empirical findings and observed effects: A promising yet still limited museum mediation

The examination of mediation practices at the museum highlights real potential. On the students’ side, interviews converge not only on a gain in concreteness—“Thanks to the visit we were able to acquire more knowledge... we would never have known what what we were taught actually looked like” (Pierrette); “I was able to see for the first time... how a rock forms, and many other things” (Tolotra)—but also on persistent barriers. The instructional sequences observed show that fruitful interactions occur when the conversation flows and spontaneous interventions from the students are welcomed. Thus, during one visit, the student Steffy interrupted the historical narrative to point out: “We had a guide, otherwise we wouldn’t have known what to do.” The mediator then paused, valorized the intervention, and redirected the exposition by integrating that viewpoint. What followed was a series of questions that turned a lecture-style presentation into a co-constructed exchange. This shift illustrates the centrality of feedback: in line with Palo Alto’s transactional model, immediate feedback stimulates engagement and supports learning. However, such moments remain too isolated: most visits follow a relatively

closed script, without explicit prompts (“Feel free to ask questions,” “What do you think?”), which keeps students in a primarily receptive role. Furthermore, the analysis also highlights a lasting tension between two horizons of expectation: heritage valorization—celebrating the nation’s geological wealth—and the curricular objectives of Life and Earth Sciences (SVT). This duality of interpretive frames produces blurring effects. On the one hand, the guide emphasizes “national mining wealth,” anchoring the visit in an identity- and heritage-oriented logic (structuring the visit in four sections: mineralogy, petrography, ores, fossils); on the other, the SVT teacher recenters the activity on the learning goal: “Today, it is essential to distinguish between mineral and ore.” In Goffman’s terms, we observe the coexistence of “frames” that assign distinct roles: students oscillate between a touristic posture (admiration, desire to take photos) and an academic posture (note-taking, conceptual questions). This competition of roles (heritage expert vs. guardian of academic knowledge) can slip into implicit rivalry, generate attentional friction, and ultimately weaken content assimilation. The socio-pragmatic context reinforces these gaps. Implicit norms—silence, distance from display cases, a tacit ban on touching—constrain sensory exploration. However, the temporary suspension of these norms tends to reactivate engagement: one student noted, “I would have liked to touch the opal, a lucky stone.” During an exceptional workshop authorizing supervised handling, enthusiasm rose markedly, attesting to the value of revisiting the “do not touch” rule. In the same vein, switching into Malagasy proved immediately mobilizing, reminding us—following Hymes—how cultural keys and genres of enunciation shape reception and audience involvement.

To this is added the competition among purposes—educational, heritage, institutional—highlighted by Mucchielli’s finalist theory. The guide must simultaneously present the collection with rigor, nurture a sense of national pride, and work within material constraints. As he acknowledges: “Our weakness is not keeping up with technological developments.” Several students mentioned the absence of audiovisual support as a shortcoming: “A video projection... showing soil and rock formation would have been the icing on the cake” (Kevin, John). These expectations reinforce the idea of an ecosystem combining short video capsules and QR codes integrated into the route. In the absence of interactive devices (screens, immersive setups) and without prior negotiation of shared objectives with the teacher, audience attention disperses for lack of a clear hierarchy of priorities.

Finally, the analysis of didactic transposition reveals breaks in the chain from scholarly knowledge → taught knowledge → displayed knowledge. Some labels remain too elliptical for immediate pedagogical use. The statement “Lithium: source of batteries” specifies neither the geological context nor formation processes or environmental issues, making it difficult for students to understand. As one teacher lamented: “I can’t rely on this label to illustrate my lesson.” This discontinuity hampers the integration of museum resources with SVT objectives and reduces the exhibition’s educational reach.

In summary, articulating the five models converges on a shared diagnosis: (i) genuinely dialogic interactions exist but remain rare (Palo Alto); (ii) the co-presence of heritage and school frames generates role confusion (Goffman); (iii) implicit norms—especially the tactile ban—limit sensory engagement, despite promising linguistic adjustments (Hymes); (iv) the plurality of purposes, compounded by material constraints, dilutes the message (Mucchielli); and (v) the transposition chain is frequently interrupted, limiting

didactic transferability (Chevallard). Hence the need for a systemic approach: the spiral of geo-didactic mediation, designed to synchronize interactions, frames, norms, purposes, and pedagogical continuity, and to make the museum a space for the co-construction of knowledge.

Revising museum mediation through a systemic integration of theoretical models
The results show that the pedagogical effectiveness of the National Museum of Geology in Ampandrianomby (MNG) depends less on the breadth of its collections than on the museum's ability to coherently articulate educational and heritage frames, implicit visiting norms, and didactic continuity. Such articulation requires finely adjusting the museum's communication practices.

Integrating the five theoretical models highlights several success conditions. Guides should be able to identify and capitalize on moments of positive feedback (Palo Alto), explicitly frame the visit upstream to align educational and heritage objectives (Goffman), carefully manage implicit norms (including the prohibition on touching), and make appropriate use of the local language (Hymes). In addition, priorities for the visit should be jointly clarified to avoid contradictory instructions (Mucchielli), and to ensure continuity of content compatible with the curriculum (Chevallard).

None of these frameworks is sufficient on its own for grasping the complexity of educational mediation in a museum setting; their combination, however, allows for the construction of an approach that is both sustainable and operational. The Palo Alto transactional perspective reminds us that feedback is structuring: the guide's recognition of a student's question converts the unidirectional presentation into a dialogical exchange—mediation is only effective if it continuously integrates visitors' reactions. These sequences nevertheless unfold within a stabilized social context. From a Goffmanian perspective, the roles—teacher, guide, students—are anchored by distinct institutional expectations (school frame vs. heritage frame). Without any explicit device (a joint teacher–guide briefing, statement of expectations), participants oscillate between a learner's posture and an observer's posture.

Hymes's sociopragmatic model reveals the effects of implicit norms (no touching, sometimes no photographing) and linguistic keys (timely switching into Malagasy) that structure the experience. What could hinder engagement (tactile bans, register shifts) becomes, at the MNG, an opportunity to refocus attention if these rules are made explicit and temporarily adjusted. In parallel, Mucchielli's finalist theory reminds us that mediators pursue multiple aims—scientific valorization, identity pride, management of logistical constraints—that may come into tension. A coherent discourse requires prior negotiation of these aims and the designation of a shared priority objective for each visit (e.g., prioritizing rock formations over their economic value).

Finally, didactic transposition (Chevallard) clarifies the gaps between scholarly knowledge and displayed knowledge. Labels that are too elliptical or decoupled from the curriculum impede acquisition. Hence the need for a didactic continuum: each label and each activity / animation should be designed in close articulation with SVT curriculum notions, to ensure the flow of knowledge from the scientific to the taught and then to the displayed.

By combining these contributions, mediation at the MNG can be rethought as a systemic process articulating complementary phases (object, narrative, manipulation, question). This logic, formalized as the spiral of geo-didactic mediation, mobilizes the most relevant

model at each stage: feedback loops (Palo Alto), explicit social framing (Goffman), temporary lifting of norms and cultural/linguistic adjustment (Hymes), clarification of aims (Mucchielli), and pedagogical continuity (Chevallard). An integrated—rather than segmented— approach allows for a sustainable improvement in the MNG's educational impact and provides a framework that can be transferred to other institutions in Africa and beyond, supporting museum outreach that combines education and culture. Outputs and operational contributions — Modeling proposal: Spiral of geo-didactic mediation

Principles and implementation

The central, directly actionable and transferable contribution is the formalization of an integrated approach—the spiral of geo-didactic mediation—that links practical recommendations to theoretical foundations. It unfolds in four complementary phases, each anchored in one or more of the mobilized models.

The spiral proposes to orchestrate the visit as a continuous movement that returns several times to the same conceptual core, changing at each passage the mode of entry into knowledge: first through the object and perception, then through narrative that situates and makes sense, next through manipulation that transforms observation into investigation, and finally through the question that stabilizes conceptualization. This dynamic responds directly to field findings: tension between heritage and academic frames^{10, 15}, tactile frustration and need for audiovisual supports^{11–12, 14–15}, dialogic “sparks” that remain too contingent^{9, 11}. It is grounded in a transactional logic (Palo Alto), explicit framing (Goffman), norms and sociopragmatic keys (Hymes), arbitration of aims (Mucchielli), and alignment of scholarly–taught–displayed knowledge (Chevallard). The goal is not to add up “activities,” but to ensure an intelligible continuity between what one sees, what one understands, what one does, and what one can explain in class.

1) The object: Presenting Geological Artifacts in a Tangible Way

Supported by didactic transposition (Chevallard) and the sensory dimension (Hymes), entry through the object immediately establishes a relationship with the perceptible properties that underlie geological categories. It recommends creating a secure tactile area with durable samples chosen for their demonstrative value—a granite with easily distinguishable crystals, a well-formed quartz, a fossil with legible relief—and a clearly defined authorization to touch (boundaries, duration, expected gestures)^{11–12}, initiate learning through a strong sensory and emotional experience conducive to durable cognitive consolidation.

This negotiated lifting of the “do not touch” norm does not contravene collection protection; it recontextualizes it by distinguishing between manipulable pieces and sensitive display cases. Perception thus becomes a didactic operation: looking, comparing, naming, classifying. On labels, a dual entry makes the object reusable in class: a “SVT concept” box alongside a brief perceptual description and a minimal lexicon^{14–15}.

2) Narrative: Contextualize and Narrate to create meaning

Moving to narrative means linking the object to a trajectory—geological genesis, provenance, uses, sometimes local memory—to build situated intelligibility. At the MNG, based on Goffman’s interactionism and Mucchielli’s semio-contextual/multifinal

approach, this step leverages heritage anchoring without losing sight of the curricular target. It offers short, “dual-entry” pedagogical sheets (composed of short paragraphs) for each manipulable object, ideally bilingual (French/Malagasy). These weave together a local, historical, or anecdotal story (e.g., discovery of a fossil in Majunga; legends associated with minerals) and a scientific notion from the curriculum (quartz crystal structure; fossilization process). QR codes point to short explanatory videos (rock formation, mineral transformation)¹⁴⁻¹⁵. The aim is to explicitly harmonize academic (scientific) and heritage (cultural) frames so as to make them complementary and non-competitive—the systematic use of the local language strengthening cultural relevance and accessibility.

3) Manipulation: prioritize direct, guided interaction

Learning by doing, manipulation turns observation into procedure: weighing, comparing, lightly scratching, using a hand lens, confronting with a reference sample. Anchored in sociopragmatics (Hymes) and multiple aims (Mucchielli), this phase explicitly and temporarily lifts the tactile ban for a selection of objects, within a secure protocol supported by mediators. It requires a defined perimeter and brief instructions; it suspends, for a limited time, the non-contact rule and replaces it with a rule of action (what is expected, why, when)¹¹⁻¹². “Learning is actively constructing meaning, not receiving information.” — 7. At the MNG, visitor-flow constraints do not preclude the workshop; they dictate its simplicity: a fixed station, a stabilized piece, a prompt leading to an observable result. The museum is reconfigured as a “laboratory of exploration”: material experimentation fuels conceptual understanding, engages body and emotion, and supports motivation for the Earth Sciences.

4) The question: institute dialogic loops and clarify aims

Co-constructing and stabilizing conceptualization, the question is not an add-on; it is the engine that converts experience into concept. Inspired by Palo Alto (circular feedback) and Mucchielli (clarifying objectives), this phase structures exchanges where the question becomes a lever for making thinking explicit.

It requires a preliminary briefing (30-minutes) between guide and teacher to settle on a priority objective, a target lexicon, and a few pivot questions (e.g., “understand the formation of sedimentary rocks”). Above all, it requires a culture of feedback during the visit: the guide is trained to identify and enhance each intervention through “dialogic triggers” (reformulation, follow-up prompt, linking back to the manipulated object), turning contributions into learning steps^{9, 11}.

By articulating object → narrative → manipulation → question, the spiral synchronizes interactions, frames, norms, aims, and pedagogical continuity. This device offers a simple-to-implement yet conceptually robust framework to strengthen the MNG’s educational impact and to offer a model adaptable to other science museums.

Practical Contributions—The Geo-Didactic Mediation Spiral

Geo-didactic mediation spiral (compact)

Figure 1. Geo-didactic mediation spiral.

Perspective and implications

These results confirm the value of an explicit museum pedagogy that converses with the curriculum and places the learner at the center of a system where hands-on experience is not an add-on but a driver of intelligibility. In the Malagasy context, the challenge is twofold: clarifying the objectives of each visit and reestablishing the didactic continuity that enables movement from label to classroom. Beyond a single session, the spiral aims to contribute to students' science capital by multiplying opportunities for meaningful contact with scientific knowledge.

Moreover, the findings resonate with Falk and Dierking's Contextual Model of Learning, which conceives that: "Museum learning emerges from intertwined personal, sociocultural, and physical contexts." — 8. The spiral operates across all three: perceptual anchoring, situated contextualization, and purpose-driven questioning. In the vein of Hooper-Greenhill, the visit embraces explicit, equipped learning intentions without "schoolifying" the museum. The literature on science capital suggests that

combining objects, narratives, and practices multiplies meaningful contacts with science and strengthens students' self-efficacy. In terms of purposes and transposition, the spiral disciplines heritage orientation in service of a curricular target and provides materials reusable in class.

Strategic recommendations for developing the National Museum of Geology in Ampandrianomby

Orientations are recommended for scaling up the approach, and are located at the institution-level: they create the conditions for sustainable deployment of the spiral without duplicating its content. To sustainably enhance the museum's influence—within Africa and internationally—while overcoming current inertia, we propose a coordinated implementation of four immediate levers. First, consolidate the museum's digital presence—a curated, accessible website and ongoing social media publishing—will increase the MNG's visibility. Educational anchoring should be formalized through agreements with schools and universities (annual pathways, outdoor classes, training days). A partnership network (mining sector, local companies, peer museums, sponsorship) will support tactile facilities and traveling exhibitions. For distant audiences, hybrid formats (lean virtual tours, lightweight AR) will extend access without substituting for the on-site experience: the on-site visit remains the locus of the spiral; with digital technology serving as its gateway and scaffolding.

1) Structured digital outreach

Establish an interactive website and maintain a regular editorial presence on social media. The content strategy will combine narrative formats (object stories, researcher profiles), explanatory videos, and playful quizzes on Malagasy geology. Designed for mediation and visibility of collections and research, this digital ecosystem will broaden audiences—including internationally—and position the museum as a scientific reference point.

2) Recurring educational programs aligned with the curriculum

Roll out regular themed pathways (outdoor classes, simulated digs, micro-lectures) co-constructed with schools and universities. The aim is to embed museum visits within the national curriculum (notably SVT—Life and Earth Sciences) by aligning learning objectives, materials, and assessments, thereby sustaining youth engagement.

3) Partnerships and sponsorship for equipment and itinerancy

Build a partner network (mining sector, local businesses, international museum organizations, cultural sponsors) to secure ongoing funding for tactile and digital equipment (manipulation areas, interactive devices). These partnerships will also facilitate traveling exhibitions—a “beyond-the-walls” vector of visibility for the MNG.

4) Hybrid and immersive experiences

Develop hybrid exhibitions that combine on-site visits with virtual pathways (augmented reality/360° tours) to reach distant audiences and students in less accessible regions. This dual access offers an immersive experience that extends the visit, both online and in person, and strengthens inclusivity of the cultural offerings.

Taken together, these measures aim to make the MNG not only a site of heritage preservation but also an innovative educational and cultural space where multimodal, participatory mediation is actively tested. Alignment with national educational objectives and Madagascar's scientific and tourism development goals provides the throughline.

Research contributions in scientific museum mediation

This study offers substantial contributions, both empirically and theoretically, as well as operationally.

Empirical contribution. Empirically, the study documents—for the first time in Madagascar—mediation practices in a science museum from a triangulated corpus combining nineteen interviews and roughly six hours of observation. This empirical anchoring provides a solid basis for analyzing actual mediation practices.

Theoretical contribution. Theoretically, it demonstrates the value of an architecture of complementarity among Palo Alto’s transactionalism, Goffman’s interactionism, Hymes’s sociopragmatics, Mucchielli’s finalist approach, and Chevallard’s didactic transposition, to articulate micro-interactions, the social structuring of roles, the effects of norms and registers, the orientation of aims, and the continuity of knowledge.

Operational contribution. It formalizes a systemic framework—the spiral of geo-didactic mediation—specifically testable in situ and reusable by other institutions in African contexts. The spiral articulates object, narrative, manipulation, and question, assigning to each phase the most pertinent theoretical models to guide the design and evaluation of devices.

Societal and educational contribution. The research highlights the key role of science museums in developing Malagasy youths’ science capital—a lever for career orientation and civic engagement. Bourdieu & Darbel said that: “Museum visits require learned codes; making them explicit reduces access inequalities.” — 9. By offering sensory, narrative, interactive, and reflective experiences, the MNG can move beyond conservation alone to become a learning environment aligned with Madagascar’s educational and cultural needs.

Toward institutionalizing pedagogy

To ensure the educational dimension over time, the MNG could establish a mediation unit responsible for designing and evaluating a training program for guides (instructional design, prompting techniques, management of norms). The unit would ensure pedagogical alignment (standard briefings, standardized of didactic labels), evaluate the impact of the spiral through pre/post protocols (knowledge, motivation), study the effect of facilitation language (Malagasy/French) on engagement and understanding, and coordination with educational partners. The spiral provides the “grammar” of professional practices on the gallery floor; the unit provides the steering.

Scope and limitations of the study

The fieldwork, centered on a high school in the capital and a cohort of fifteen students, does not claim statistical representativeness. The presence of the researcher may have influenced some behaviors. The lack of longitudinal measures prevents assessment of the durability of learning gains. Finally, the available documentation was not homogeneous across galleries, which may have constrained some comparisons.

Toward a sustainable embedding of pedagogy within the museum

The MNG has rare assets—substantial collections, historical anchoring, heritage legitimacy. Converting this potential into durable educational gains requires careful orchestration of interactions, frames, and norms, with clarity about aims and firm

anchoring in the curriculum.

The results converge toward a common goal: to make the MNG a structuring actor in science mediation, where each visit is part of a continuous pedagogical chain and a culturally pertinent mediation, serving a broader public with sustained engagement. In short, the study shows that the MNG's pedagogical effectiveness rests on mediation that is both integrated and explicit. Its success depends on the fine articulation of interactional, interpretive, pragmatic, finalist, and didactic dimensions—an alignment that conditions both learning quality and clarity of objectives. From this perspective, the proposed operational approach—the spiral of geo-didactic mediation—constitutes a structuring lever: it directs mediation toward a clear educational purpose consistent with the SVT curriculum and the expectations of Madagascar's school system.

By virtue of its practicality (clear procedures, simple tools) and transferability (a framework adaptable to various museum contexts), the spiral offers a sustainable implementation path: it promotes staff ownership, didactic continuity of content, and the integration of pedagogy at the heart of visitor itineraries (visit pathways). Beyond the MNG, it opens perspectives applicable to other science museums in African contexts and, more broadly, on an international scale—positioning the museum as a learning environment where the experience is at once sensory, narrative, interactive, and reflective.

Notes and Sources

1. Law no. 2006-030 on the protection of Madagascar's intangible cultural heritage 25.
2. Henri Bésairie 26 and Alfred Lacroix 27, co-founders of the MNG.
3. Approx. 27,000 pieces (minerals, rocks, fossils): internal data collected during fieldwork.
9. Student “Steffy,” Lycée Gallieni, May 2023.
10. Guide #1 interview, MNG, May 2023.
11. Participant observation, guided visit, MNG, May 2023.
12. Student “Kaiann,” Lycée Gallieni, May 2023.
14. Permanent-exhibit label: “Lithium: source for batteries.”
15. SVT teacher interview, Lycée Gallieni, May 2023.

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Biography

Bio — Mihaja Randrianja

Mihaja Randrianja, lecturer-researcher in Information and Communication Sciences at the University of Antananarivo and the University of Vakinakaratra (STICOM), specializes in museum communication and mediation in Madagascar. She explores school–museum relations, linguistic and social accessibility of content, and interpretation tools. Drawing on fieldwork in Antananarivo and Antsirabe, she applies the IEC (Inform–Educate–Communicate) framework to analyze practices and design operational tools. She teaches organizational communication and contributes to heritage enhancement projects, focusing on governance and educational museum capital.

Bio — Tianarisoa Andriamanga

Tianarisoa Andriamanga, lecturer-researcher in semiotics and film studies at the University of Antananarivo and the University of Vakinakaratra (STICOM), investigates narrative and visual forms (film, photography, posters, multimedia) and their circulation in the public sphere. His research emphasizes cultural communication and mediation, blending discourse semiotics, film analysis, and qualitative methods. He supervises students in media and advertising communication (storytelling, image analysis, visual

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Bio — Jean-Jules Harijaona

Jean-Jules Harijaona, Full Professor at the University of Antananarivo, is a specialist in French didactics, sociolinguistics, and information and communication sciences. He co-founded the “Communication in French” program and the STICOM Department (Sciences and Techniques of Information and Communication). His research focuses on media and political communication. Beyond academia, he has contributed as a consultant for candidates in various elections, bridging scientific expertise and practical communication strategies.